

List of Quality Assessment Criteria

Assessment Question	Number of papers	Primary Studies
QA1: How clearly is the problem of study described?	88% (37/42) of the studies clearly describe the research problem	[4][68][78][69][80][81][76][74][82][63][67][77][57][62][73] [5][65][88][64][61][79][83][52][54][53][84][89][66][55][56][60][58][85][72] [59][87][90]
	11.9% (5/42) of the studies describe the problem vaguely	[75] [91] [89] [71] [90]
QA2 : How clearly is the research context stated?	26.2% (11/42) of the studies generally describe the context of the research	[73][53][75][66][91][89][71][56][60][58][85]
	73.8% (31/42) of the primary studies present references addressing the research context.	[4][68][78][69][80][81] [76][74][82][63][67][77][57][70] [62] [5][65][88][64][61][79][83][52][54][84][89][55][72][86][66][90]
QA3: How rigorously is the method evaluated?	64.3% (27/42) of the studies evaluate their solutions using case studies	[69][4][80][81][76][74] [67] [77] [62][73][5][65][88][64][61] [79][83][54][75][89][66][86][55][90][59][72][70]
	16.7% (7/42) of the studies report no evaluation	[63][53][91][71][58][87][88]
	11.9% (5/42) of the studies use an experiment where the assumptions about the approach are statistically supported and can be reproduced based on the experimental design using different samples	[68][78][82][57][60]

	7,1% (3/42) papers present lessons learned, conveying their practical perspective. This analysis highlights the need for more controlled experimental studies to reinforce the validity of the approaches proposed in trust requirements for sociotechnical	[52] [86] [70]
QA4: How explicitly are the contributions presented?	78.6\% (33/42) of the studies expressly present their contribution. We paid particular attention to the synthesis of the results, the evaluation methods, and how they explicitly address the solution to the problem	[68][4][69][78][80][81] [76] [74] [82] [63][67][77][57][70][62] [5] [65][88][64][61][79][83][52][54] [84][66][55][75][60][58][90][59][73]
	19,0% (8/42) papers address their contributions more broadly, and 2,38% (1/42) paper does not present it explicitly	[53][89][56][91][86][71][85][72]
QA5: How explicitly are the insights and issues for future work stated?	28.57% (12/42) of the studies include specific guidelines for future research	[82][78][53][68][69][80][81][76] [73][87][86][91]
	57.14%(24/42) of the studies provide only general ideas for future work	[63][77][57][62][5][65][88][74] [64][61][79][83][52][54][84][89] [55][75][60][58][90][59][72][91]
	14.29% (6/42) of the studies do not provide concrete recommendations for future work	[66][56][91][86][71][85]